

TRADITIONAL SINGING AND TRADITIONAL MUSIC SKILLS

Kholmirezayeva Feruza Mamaraim qizi¹

Khojageldiyev Erkin Amanovich²

Chorshanbiyev Jasur Nasriddin oglu³

¹ Termez State University Pedagogical Institute

Lecturer at the Department of Music Education and Fine Arts,

^{2,3} Masters in Music Education and Arts

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ABSTRACT

In this article, I will focus on the art of maqom, one of the oldest forms of art. prose and difficulty categories are given. Music from ancient art from its own process with the social life of mankind to the present day continues to form depending on. There is great work to be done in its development the ground for the future.

The art of national maqom, which is an integral part of the cultural heritage of our people, is ancient spiritual with its history, deep philosophical roots, unique artistic style and rich creative traditions plays an important role in our lives. For centuries, great poets and scholars, skilled composers, the hard work and dedication of singers and musicians, inspired by their creative thinking This unique art is coming not only in our country and in the East, but also around the world has gained great fame and attention. Shashmaqom, the flower of maqom art, is UNESCO recognized as an intangible cultural heritage of mankind by and The fact that it is included in the representative list is a clear confirmation of this.

About the study and development of the art of maqom in our country over the past

period certain work has been done. In particular, the publication of the text of the Uzbek note "Shashmaqom" and according to them, the recording of maqom songs on magnetic tapes is huge was an event of scientific and cultural significance.

The characteristic feature of the status quo is the depth of the mind, all of the spiritual virtues based on logical thinking to achieve mental perfection by consciously mastering its facets. Folk songs, maqoms are not limited in scope. Examples of this execution according to the age characteristics of the students, their worldview, the level of moral and aesthetic development inclusion in textbooks increases students' morale in the learning process. Education now The main purpose of music education in educational institutions is the national music of the younger generation to grow

up in a spirit of respect for our heritage. Experts emphasize that the classical maqom lines have an elegant and heartfelt, deep philosophical meaning I have been enjoying our people for a long time.

The fact that the status quo has existed for centuries is due to a number of factors, particularly the teacher hafizu closely related to the high performance skills of the musicians. Folk music the criterion that reflects the live process is the executive practice.

Music is one of the ancient arts from the process of its formation to the present day formed and developed in connection with the social life of mankind. A variety of life systems musical samples were constructed based on the conditions. On the way to its own development laid the groundwork for the emergence of large-scale works. The complexity of our musical heritage and Perfect aspects, rich potential of the art of music are important in human life For the performer, the talent is a meaningful expression, feeling the music in the heart The science of music (musical patterns, genres, their composition and metrorhythmic aspects, execution technique, execution skills).

Musical art is one of the most important factors in master music performance. "Everyone the musician knows that he can sing raga, for which he can feel a certain depth bas. However, it is not the "singing" of the raga feeling to them, but the delicacy that is created in the raga, gives a musical instrument that expresses feelings such as sadness and amazement. (translated by B.S.) - describes the famous Indian musicologist Ragkhaeva R. Mennon. In fact, the singer is the first performer and the first listener of his musical interpretation. After all, the performer enriches his skills

by singing in the interpretation of the instrument. Sozanda the more skillfully he achieves the perfect expression of a musical work on the instrument, and the more proportionate The more he can influence the singing, the more he will have the secrets of the art of accompaniment. His key features such as alertness, sensitivity, badiha, rational interpretation and constant control Maqoms are present in the musical heritage of many peoples of the East. They are these peoples forms the basis of national music. Statuses have a theoretical and practical basis, is a masterpiece of the musical art of these peoples. The status is particularly Uzbek and the spiritual property of the Tajik people, Shashmaqom has been in this field for many centuries is the result of creative research conducted. Master musicians and singers are the eyes of the next generation like a pupil, it has come down to us with care. Status patterns are sophisticated today as one of the richest, most incomparable treasures of the art of music in the world became truly public property. Maqom is a series of musical complexes created in a certain order, a composition of the past is a kind of polished work of art. In a broad sense, maqoms are folk music encyclopedia. Because, especially in Shashmaqom, the melodies of Uzbek folk music are rhythmic features, circle methods, poetry is based on the rules of connection of folk songs a number of fronts have been expressed, so that the study of status issues now, attaches great importance to the identification and adoption of methods of status performance. What is status? The Arabic term "place" and "place" were used to form instruments place, that is, the curtain and represents a set of melodies and songs that

correspond to them. Commentary on Giyosul-Lughat The author of the encyclopedia, Muhammad Giyosuddin, is a scholar of the past and present Based on his comments, he described the phrase maqom as follows: Goyand "means Maqom on the screen of melodies and songs. Here melodies and songs the starting curtain as well as the fret sound lines they move, of course.

The word maqom is associated with the notions of melody and tone, and their surface The history of the arrival dates back to ancient times, when professional music appeared. The melodies of the maqoms are based on the unique musical riches of each nation, the artist formed in the process of long historical and cultural development by musicians, singers and composers It is known from ancient sources on music that the status of historical, theoretical and practical bodies there are sides.

Their theoretical problems were solved by al-Kindi, who lived and worked in the IX-XVII centuries. Al-Farabi, al-Khwarizmi, Ibn Sina, al-Urmavi, Shirazi, Maraghi, Jami, Husseini, Kawkabi, In the treatises of great scholars such as Darvishali Changi, commentaries are made on a deep scientific basis given. It should be noted that the theory of music in all the peoples of the East, with some differences except that it was almost the same. Even the names of the bodies and branches was similar. However, their melodies are unique and radically different from each other.

The system of "Twelve maqoms" / "Twelve maqoms" / in the musical-theoretical treatises of the past and the 24 branches that make up it are considered 6 votes / Currently among some scholars there are a

number of puzzles that have caused controversy.

The performance of such a status instrument in our country is expected It should be noted that Most importantly, the teaching process is based on notes and based on modern pedagogical technologies. For example, note based on the rapid acquisition of status melodies and their structure, ie bars, room, the ability to master the basics and the basics at an early age gives An example in this regard is the Classification of the Status of Shashmaqom Buzruk Buzruk Note the work.

Although Uzbek musical instruments are very rich in type and sound, but the conditions and depending on their capabilities, some types of them are used in the performance of the status ensemble daughter in law. For example, according to Professor Abdurauf Fitrat (1884-1938), the twentieth century.

In the 1920s, the Uzbek maqom ensemble played two tanburs, a dutar, and a davra. used, if the tanbur is three, the third tanbur is performed as a sato with a bow.¹ Also, in many cases, the singers played the instruments themselves parts of the instrument were also performed by them. The situation from the 30s of the twentieth century the form of ensemble performance improved, and with the formation of this group of musicians explained. Today, Uzbek maqom ensembles are professional musicians and consists of groups of singers. Accompanying the singers is a priority for the group is. Professional musicians play an important role in the performance of Uzbek maqom instruments requires extensive professional training. Because status is an ensemble performance is important in two ways: 1) the skill of the musicians in collaboration increases by means of; 2) the

possibilities and scope of maqom instrumental performance expands. Maqom is a solo form of instrumental performance. The status is played by an instrument Solo is the lead performance of a particular musician on his own instrument understood. For example, the musician of the Kashgar rubobi is accompanied by a single instrument can act as a soloist. Status works are colorful two or three instruments to a particular instrument due to its richness of properties (For example, Kashgar rubobi-gijjak + doira; Kashgar rubobi-chang + doira, etc.). Because it is known that maqom music is rich in features.

The Uzbek form of solo performance has great potential to attract attention; 1) Soloist fully demonstrates his skills; 2) status tool allows you to expand the performance on the basis of individual performance style; 3) mohir a mechanism emerges for musicians to gain status. So, the situation in the future forming an individual performance style to train solo musicians required. Maqom is an amateur form of instrumental performance. The Uzbek status belongs to the musician himself one of its distinctive features is that it has an amateur shape. Amateur status tool There are two types of performance:

1) in youth music schools, clubs, ensembles in clubs and individual groups; 2) the status of districts, cities and regions ensembles. An amateur who meets certain requirements in accordance with regulatory documents groups are called "folk ensembles". Maqom is an amateur form of instrumental performance has a number of opportunities: 1) to educate and guide talented young people; 2) youth realization of their potential; 3) popularization of status performance; 4) Community culture ensuring the prestige of the art of maqom at the level of Hence, forms of maqom performance have their own characteristics and their development is a state of instrumental performance as practical mechanisms of development.

Emphasize when the time comes performers who perform in all forms of maqom instrumental performance has a talent and musical education. Therefore, it is necessary to develop these forms of performance important. In this regard, the status of future musicians in the process of music education should be accustomed to working with all forms of performance. Because the future status In the future, musicians will be able to perform in the form of maqom instruments.

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